

STABILITY OF EXTEMPORANEOUS ORAL VANCOMYCIN FORMULATIONS FOR CLOSTRIDIODES DIFFICILE INFECTION: 90-DAY ANALYSIS

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INTRODUCTION

Clostridioides difficile infection (CDI) is one of the main healthcare-associated infections and a leading cause of antibiotic-associated diarrhea, with significant hospital impact [1]. The rising incidence has prompted strengthened epidemiological surveillance by national authorities, aligning with World Health Organization's recommendations, and current guidelines from the European Society of Clinical Microbiology and the Infectious Diseases and Infectious Diseases Society of America recommend oral vancomycin (VCM) formulations for the treatment primary non-severe episodes, and European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing v14.0 identifies it as clinically appropriate for susceptible strains ($MIC \leq 2$ mg/L) [2]. This increasing trend incidence in Portugal supports the need for patients to complete treatment at home, avoiding unnecessary hospitalization and thereby minimizing the risk of transmitting healthcare-associated infections spread, supported by hospital pharmacy-prepared extemporaneous formulations that meet European (Ph.Eur.) and United States Pharmacopeias (USP) quality, safety, and efficacy standards [3,4], in collaboration with the Clinical Pathology Service and the microbiology department.

OBJETIVES

To evaluate the physicochemical and microbiological stability of oral VCM solutions at 25 mg/mL, stored under refrigeration (UR: 2-8 °C) and controlled room temperature (CRT: 25 °C, <60% RH) for up to 90 days, assessing recovery under each storage condition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An experimental, longitudinal *in vitro* study was performed to evaluate the physicochemical and microbiological stability of oral VCM solutions (25 mg/mL). Four batches were compounded using water for injection, stored in

amber glass vials, and prepared from different commercial brands. Each sample was serially diluted from 25 mg/mL to 25 µg/mL to evaluate the method's limit of detection. Three replicate analyses per sample were performed to ensure statistical robustness. Samples were analyzed at time points: Days 0, 7, 14, 21, 30, 45, 60, 75, and 90. Physicochemical stability was assessed by immunochemiluminescence, with stability defined as 90-110% recovery of the initial concentration. pH was determined by potentiometry, and visual inspection was performed to detect precipitate formation. Microbiological stability was evaluated using a colorimetric method and BacT/ALERT[®] microbial growth detection according to institutional protocol with the Pathology Service, and microbiology department. Statistical analysis included calculation of mean \pm standard deviation (SD), linear regression modeling, and Student's t-test to compare differences between time points and batches. All analyses were performed using SPSS v28, with p-values <0.05 considered statistically significant. This methodology enabled rigorous evaluation of VCM stability under both refrigerated and controlled room temperature conditions.

RESULTS

The stability study demonstrated that, under different storage conditions and for all tested samples, remained stable for over 21 days, within the defined recovery range of 90-110%, exceeding the maximum stability period for oral solutions recommended by the Ph. Eur. and USP. The mean recoveries for samples stored UR were 105.1 \pm 2.4% for Batch A and 98.2 \pm 1.7% for Batch C, both falling within the predefined stability acceptance range, as illustrated in Figure 1. Solutions stored at CRT showed recoveries below the acceptable range subsequent to day 30, with 83.4 \pm 2.0% and 76.9 \pm 1.9% for Batches B and D, respectively, indicating progressive stability loss, reaching 59.5 \pm 2.3% by the end of the 90-day study, as presented on Table 1.

SAMPLE, % Recovery ± Standard Deviation				
Study Day	Batch A	Batch B	Batch C	Batch D
0	104.5±1.1	103.8±2.7	105.2±1.8	104.5±2.8
7	105.0±1.2	96.5±1.1	101.7±1.2	102.9±3.3
14	101.5±2.1	96.7±0.9	98.3±1.4	97.0±2.8
21	103.2±2.8	95.4±2.2	98.6±1.2	90.6±3.1
30	97.7±1.4	83.5±2.1	100.5±0.7	83.1±2.0
45	105.1±2.4	83.4±2.0	98.2±1.7	76.9±1.9
60	99.4±1.5	77.5±2.8	99.9±0.8	71.4±2.3
75	106.4±2.8	73.9±2.2	103.2±2.1	71.3±3.5
90	91.4±2.8	60.1±2.8	91.2±2.8	59.5±2.3

Table 1. Recovery of VCM (%), expressed as mean ±SD.

Statistical analysis using Student's t-test showed no significant differences between conditions up to day 21, while highly significant differences were observed after day 30 ($p < 0.001$). Linear regression analysis revealed different degradation rates UR ($R^2 = 0.138$; $p = 0.009$) and CRT conditions ($R^2 = 0.873$; $p < 0.001$), indicating degradation approximately 7.4 times faster at CRT. These results are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Stability of oral VCM solutions over 90 days.

Visual inspection of CRT-stored solutions revealed precipitate formation from day 35, confirming instability under these conditions. Throughout the 90-day study, the pH of all formulations remained stable, with no significant variation. Throughout the study period, no microbiological contamination was observed, confirming the safety of the oral VCM solutions.

CONCLUSION

The oral pharmaceutical form of VCM, as compounded in this study, enables adherence to the standard-of-care therapeutic regimen for non-severe cases of CDI in isolation, in accordance with the recommendations of the Portuguese Directorate-General of Health NOC 019/2014 [5]. Based on the results and the robustness of the data obtained, VCM solutions were considered stable UR conditions for at least 90 days, supporting their feasibility for home administration, enabling eligible patients to complete therapy without hospitalization, contributing to the sustainability of the National Health Service, generating pharmacoeconomic benefits, improving patient quality of life, and reducing the risk of healthcare-associated infection's dissemination.

This study underscores the critical role of hospital pharmacists in the preparation and validation of compounded medications, demonstrating that rigorous pharmaceutical practice, strict adherence to Good Preparation Practices standards, technical and scientific validation expertise are essential to ensure the quality, safety, and efficacy of compounded formulations. A prospective study involving the development and evaluation of the formulation's efficacy will be performed after the implementation of this formulation.

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